

Homework: Transistor Simulation and Design

Introduction: Metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) play a critical role in memory technologies, including SRAM, DRAM, and Flash memory. This homework explores transistor design and scaling behaviors.

Sign up for an account on nanohub (<https://nanohub.org/>). Start the simulation tool “Semiconductor Machine Learning Models and Database (semldb)” (<https://nanohub.org/tools/semldb/>)

Choose Planar N-MOS on the top left Select Device box. The input parameters are the device parameters, which can be varied by dragging a dot on a bar, or double-clicking the number and typing in a value.

Select Device: Planar NMOS

Device Schematic

An NMOS (n-channel metal-oxide-semiconductor) transistor is a core device in CMOS technology, used extensively in digital and analog integrated circuits. The performance and scalability of NMOS transistors are governed by several critical physical and process parameters. In this database, three parameters are varied – gate length (L_g), high-k oxide thickness (t_{HfO_2}), and source/drain junction depth ($X_{j,SD}$) – while other parameters are held constant.

Device Parameters

Gate Length L_g [nm]	<input type="range" value="32.0"/>	32.0
High-k Oxide Thickness t_{HfO_2} [nm]	<input type="range" value="2.0"/>	2.0
S/D Junction Depth $X_{j,SD}$ [nm]	<input type="range" value="40.0"/>	40.0

Get Data from Database

GET DATA

Simulate with ML model

RUN ML MODEL

View Mode:
 ✓ Drain current vs. Gate voltage
 Drain current vs. Drain voltage
 gm vs. Gate voltage
 SS vs. Gate voltage

I_D vs. V_G

- I-V plots:** The default Device Parameters are: gate length $L_g = 32\text{nm}$, high- κ oxide thickness $t_{HfO_2} = 2.0\text{nm}$, S/D junction depth $X_{j,SD} = 40\text{nm}$. Simulate the device with ML model (click “RUN ML MODEL” button). The simulation results can be chosen from the View Mode dropdown list
 - Plot the drain current vs. gate voltage I_D vs. V_G characteristics in a linear y-axis and a log y-axis

- Plot the drain current vs drain voltage I_D vs. V_D characteristics.

(c) Read the following part, understand how to extract the on-current, off-current, and subthreshold swing: Assume a power supply voltage of $V_{DD} = 1.0V$. Based on the results, extract the following directly from the figures. If the figure reading does not provide the value at the exact V_g and V_d values required, just read from an approximate value from the bias point closest to it:

On-current, I_{on} , which is the drain current at $V_g=V_d=1.0V$. It can be read directly from the linear plot. For example, in the figure below, the value is $I_{on} = I_d(V_g = V_{DD}, V_d = V_{DD}) \approx 965 \mu A/\mu m$.

Off-current, I_{off} , which is the drain current I_d when biased at $V_g = 0V$ and $V_d = 1.0V$, $I_{off} \approx 259 nA/\mu m = 0.259 \mu A/\mu m$

Subthreshold swing (SS) at $V_g=0.1V$, $V_d = 1.0V$, $SS \approx 130 mV/dec$

2. **Gate length scaling:** (a) We will study the dependence of the on-current, off-current, and SS on transistor channel length scaling. Vary only the gate length only (L_g) and keep other parameters their default values, run ML model, and extract the I_{on} , I_{off} , and SS values following the example above, and fill the following table:

L_g [nm]	12	22	32	42	52
I_{on} [$\mu A/\mu m$]					
I_{off} [$\mu A/\mu m$]					
SS [mV/dec]					

(b) Based on the simulation results obtained in the table above, discuss how SS and off-current change as the gate length scales down from 52nm to 12nm.

3. **Junction depth design:** (a) To lower the off current for reducing the leakage power, it is preferred to have a small off current. Next, we scale down the junction depth. Fix the gate length at $L_g=40\text{nm}$, use the default value for oxide thickness, and vary the junction depth, fill the table below.

S/D junction depth $X_{j,SD}$ [nm]	30	35	40	45	50
$I_{on}[\mu A/\mu m]$					
$I_{off}[\mu A/\mu m]$					
SS[mV/dec]					

(b) Based on the table, discuss how the off-current and SS vary as the junction depth decreases. Furthermore, in transistor applications, it is desirable to have a SS below 100mV/dec. For the simulated gate length of $L_g=xx$ nm, discuss the requirements on junction depth to achieve this goal.